
Individual Submission Summary

From Panafricanism to Wokeism: Artistic Commitments to Social Justice

In Event: *Diálogos teóricos, históricos y decolonialidad del saber*

Thu, November 16, 3:30 to 5:00pm, TBA

Abstract

The paper will bear on the empowering network of transamerican and transatlantic connections woven or strengthened by committed "artists" of the Aframerican Diaspora including:

- visual artists like Caribbean-American plastician Eddy Firmin, the activist African-American painter Jonathan Harris, talented iconoclasts like Kara S. Walker, Kehinde Wiley, Ebony Patterson, the Senegalese sculptor/academician Ousmane Sow, who have dedicated their lives to social justice, Afrodiasporic visibility and reparations.

- performers heavily engaged in Transamerican networks and political action (like Maria Magdalena Campos Pons)

- film directors with outstanding achievements for the Diaspora and its iconic writers (Euzhan Palcy, for instance -> A Dry White Season, Sugar Cane Alley, her documentary on Aimé Césaire)

- researchers and cultural content producers involved in art (like Sheila S. Walker)

The main goal of this project is to reveal the "relational undercurrents" (Flores, 2017) that have historically shaped and nurtured diasporic artistic consciousness and contributed to transform the perception of Aframerican communities in the Western World thanks to artworks. We also wish to show how the articulations between Panafricanism and Wokeism in a globalized world in this respect.

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